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Growth factors expressed in breast cancer.

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Growth factors permit and sustain unlicensed cell division in cancer. In autocrine growth factor signaling, the tumor secretes and responds to its own growth factors. We measured total transcription in the normal breast and in breast cancer to discover growth factors produced by tumors in humans with breast cancer. We found multiple growth factors that were among the genes whose expression was most increased when comparing normal breast and the primary tumor. These growth factors are candidates for therapeutic targeting in breast cancer.

Results

We measured total transcription in a mixed cohort of primary tumors from humans with breast cancer.

GSE45268

$n=17$ normal breast tissues

$n=104$ primary tumors; human breast cancer

Rank	ID	p -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	%DE
3163	200896_x_at	1.50E-09	-6.55	11.1773245	-1.26	HDGF	
4507	204379_s_at	1.08E-07	-5.65	6.9996896	-2.82	FGFR3	
5818	203628_at	1.92E-06	-5.01	4.2104227	-2.27	IGF1R	
7889	202718_at	4.67E-05	-4.23	1.1437972	-1.9	IGFBP2	
8738	215179_x_at	1.22E-04	-3.97	0.2288653	-7.87E-01	PGF	
9022	223252_at	1.62E-04	-3.9	-0.0376316	-4.44E-01	HDGFRP2	
9232	221739_at	1.95E-04	-3.84	-0.2154187	-8.99E-01	MYDGF	
9937	210443_x_at	3.81E-04	-3.66	-0.844981	-5.12E-01	OGFR	
10106	236561_at	4.44E-04	-3.61	-0.9894415	-1.14	TGFBR1	/54675 total

We then measured growth factor expression in a cohort of patients with early onset breast cancer, again, a mixed cohort with respect to subtype.

GSE109169

$n=25$ normal breast tissues

$n=25$ primary tumors; human breast cancer

Rank	ID	p -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	%DE
1173	2438531	1.63E-08	-6.7	9.23176	-7.06E-01	HDGF	
1376	3377964	5.15E-08	-6.38	8.101088	-6.19E-01	FIBP	
1408	2908179	6.21E-08	-6.33	7.917396	-7.58E-01	VEGFA	
2847	3644297	8.35E-06	-4.96E+00	3.125823	-3.32E-01	GFER	
3388	3049025	2.95E-05	-4.59	1.902186	-5.25E-01	TBRG4	
3473	3892941	3.54E-05	-4.53	1.725722	-3.16E-01	OGFR	
3745	2715016	6.21E-05	-4.37	1.185355	-4.40E-01	FGFR3	
5091	2527253	6.38E-04	-3.64	-1.042406	-7.80E-01	IGFBP2	
5359	3636522	9.19E-04	-3.52	-1.386806	-4.64E-01	HDGFRP3	/19076

Discussion

We documented here expression of a vast array of growth factors and growth factor receptors, including the opioid growth factor receptor, the placental growth factor *PGF*, insulin-like growth factor receptor 1, fibroblast growth factor receptor 3, and the hepatocyte-derived growth factor *HDGF*. We also observed expression of genes from the hepatoma-derived growth factor related protein family *HDGFRP2* and *HDGFRP3*. Our study utilized only primary tumors from humans with breast cancer, and measured growth factor expression blindly using whole transcriptome technologies.

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Methods

We measured growth factor expression in human breast cancer using aforementioned microarray datasets (GSEXXXXX) and R-based computational methods.